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Comparison of an integral and a stand-alone calculations of hypothetical severe accident in a generic LW SMR with ASTEC code

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Abstract. This paper investigates a Beyond Design Basis Accident (BDBA) simulation with ASTECv3.1.1 computer code in a generic design of Light Water SMR. This design is an Integral Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR) with dry containment and electrical power 300 MW (thermal power 1000 MW).

The investigation concerns the efficiency of applying the In-Vessel Melt Retention strategy (IVMR) with external vessel water cooling in the considered SMR. The initial event that actuates the accident is double-ended guillotine break in the Direct Vessel Injection Line (DVI) and the postulated failure of all passive safety systems. The lack of all safety systems leads to impossibility the reactor core to be cooled. It creates conditions for accident progression with core overheating and slumping in the lower head of the reactor vessel – Lower Plenum (LP). At the moment of corium pouring in the LP the cavity is full with water from the Pressure Supress System (PSS) containers. So, there are conditions for investigation of all important phenomena that could be seen during the applying IVMR strategy with external vessel water cooling in the considered integral light water SMR.

An integral ASTEC input model prepared by ENEA (Italy) and modified by INRNE was used to simulate this severe accident. The integral input model represents all basic systems of the light water SMR including all safety systems. The simulation finishes with LP vessel failure due to water depletion in the cavity that trouble significantly reactor cooling. This simulation takes a month and half computation time. And it is not so suitable for uncertainty and sensitivity investigations. That's why, using the results from the integral calculation a stand-alone ASTEC input model was developed by INRNE to represent only the IVMR phase of the transient when the melted corium pool is slumped in the LP and the cavity is still filled with water. The initial and boundary conditions for the stand-alone input model have been taken from the integral calculation. The stand-alone input model has been validated against the integral input model. The calculation results of the stand-alone model are enough closer to the results from the integral input model and last for a few hours. In this way they are more appropriate for uncertainty and sensitivity investigations.

Keywords: SMR, Integral PWR, External Reactor Vessel Cooling, ASTEC, IVMR

1. Introduction

The development and implementation of integral Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) as a new nuclear technology is now increasingly discussed [1]. As a clean energy source the SMRs could serve as a supplement to the traditional large reactor designs in the energy mix. They are cheaper, with short time of licensing and establishing, and many of the SMR designs are supplied by different and independent passive safety systems, which increase significantly the safety of their exploitation [2]. Nevertheless, in some situations part of these passive safety systems or all of them could fail leading to Severe Accident (SA) [3]. That's why it is very important the safety of the SMRs to be studied deterministically and the safety of their exploitation to be confirmed [4, 1]. For this purpose, it could be used some internationally proven and validated computer codes as ASTEC, AC2, MELCOR, MAAP and others [5], for simulation of postulated SAs.

In the frame of the SASPAM-SA project (Safety Analysis of SMR with PASSive Mitigation strategies - Severe Accident) [6, 7, 8, 9] it has been initiated investigation of SMRs behaviour in case of postulated SA occurrence with different SA computer codes (ASTEC, AC2, MELCOR, MAAP, and etc.) [5]. The aim is to analyse how the different computer codes simulate the main phenomena during a postulated scenarios of accidents and to prove the ability of the codes to simulate reasonably the answer of SMR systems. The project is based on the analyses of two generic designs including the main integral PWR (iPWR) design features, considered in the most promising designs ready to go on the European market, allowing to assess in a wider way the capability of codes (SA and CFD) to simulate the phenomena typical of iPWR. It is not the project's objective to assess the generic reactor designs selected but, based on the project findings, allow a more general statement on the code's applicability to currently favoured designs under postulated SA condition.

This investigation has been done with ASTECv3.1.1 computer code [10] in the frame of SASPAM-SA project. The ASTEC code is a European computer code for representing SAs in Light Water Reactors (LWR). It has been developed initially by IRSN, France and GRS, Germany. Now its development has been continued mainly by ASNR [7, 11]. The study is based on the SASPAM-SA Design 2, a generic iPWR characterized by the use of several passive systems, a dry containment and an electric power of about 300 MWe. More information about the Design 2 can be find in [5, 12].

First a basic input model "Design2_v6.1" [13] has been provided to INRNE-BAS from ENEA institute, Bologna (Italy). This input has been modified and used from INRNE to simulate the response of the SMR in case of a guillotine break Loss of Coolant Accident (LOCA) at the Direct Vessel Injection line (DVI) and failure of all passive safety systems. The model includes all structures of SMR design as well as all passive safety systems [3]. Without activation of safety systems (e.g. through the postulated failure of correspondent valves to open), some of the accidents can escalate in SA with melting and relocation of the core into the lower head of the vessel followed by the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) rupture at very late phase compared to the existing large Nuclear Power Plant (NPP). The probability of such a critical situation is hypothetical and it is very unlikely ever to happen, but before applying any SMR design, its behaviour under extremely critical conditions should be analytically analysed. Nevertheless, that such situations could be with a very low probability, there is a need to be investigated and to look for options in design for avoiding or mitigation of severe consequences. The concept of barriers and levels of protection, which constitute the Defence in Depth (DiD) strategy, should be used for improving the safety. In this way the analytical study of the accident progressions by computer

code simulation of accident progression can be viewed as "tool" that can be used to analyse and improve barriers and protection at different levels of DiD.

The second step for INRNE-BAS was to create an input model for stand-alone calculations. This is a simplified input model that represents the part of the accident when the corium slumps into the Lower Plenum (LP) and the cavity is full with water. The transient continues till the beginning of cavity water evaporation, which obstructs core cooling [14, 15]. The stand-alone input model is simplified and could be run considerably faster than the integral input model. It could be used for investigation of the main phenomena during applying In-Vessel Melt Retention (IVMR) strategy with external vessel cooling. Therefore, the stand-alone input model is very appropriate for uncertainty and sensitivity calculations. The stand-alone input model has been validated against the results from the integral input model calculation. The initial and boundary conditions in this simplified input had been taken from the integral calculation. The results from the integral and the stand-alone calculation have been compared and discussed.

The purpose of this analysis is also to demonstrate the capabilities of the ASTEC computer code to simulate all processes and phenomena in the generic SMR design from the beginning of accident to the failure of the RPV [3].

2. Brief description of the SMR (iPWR)

Generic SMR is a medium size reactor with dry containment that produces 300MW electric power and 1000MW thermal power. All main construction elements from primary side that work at high pressure are integrated in a RPV. The reactor core, Control Rod Drive Mechanisms (CRDM), eight SGs, eight primary side pumps and a pressurizer (PRZ) are constructed inside the RPV. The reactor core is located at the bottom of the RPV. Above the reactor core there is raising channel in the center of the construction. The heat from the reactor core water flows up into the riser channel to the upper annular chamber, where it changes its direction and due to pumps head flows down in the 8th downcomer cylindrical channels. In the downcomer channels are placed the eight SGs. They are provided with secondary side bundle of helical pipes where the secondary water enters from the bottom and flows up in the opposite direction of the primary coolant flow. At the end of the bundle the secondary water has been heated to superheated steam. A simplified scheme of design is pointed in Figure 1.

At the bottom of RPV is Lower Plenum (LP). In the LP are located lower support structures and lower support rings that support lower core support plate. Above the lower core support plate is located reactor core. The reactor core contains 89 Fuel Assemblies (FA). Each FA contains about 264 fuel rods. The total mass of UO₂ is about 54385 kg. The FA are surrounded by reflector and barrel. A bypass channel is between the reflector and barrel cylindrical structures. Between the barrel and the vessel is the downcomer channel. Above the core is located upper core support plate. The continuation of the barrel cylindrical structure above the core region forms central riser channel. Above the upper annular chamber is constructed perforated steel plate that separates the PRZ. The PRZ is inside the upper head of the RPV. Its height is about 4.4 m.

The vessel is surrounded by a metal sphere with diameter of about 25 m and thickness of about 4.4 cm. In the sphere there is a concrete plate, which divide the sphere in two parts. The upper part serves as a containment "DRYWELL". The height of the upper hemisphere is about 11.7 m. The volume of the DRYWELL is about 3227 m³. The bottom part is constructed to support the RPV and the basic passive safety system - Pressure Suppress System Tanks (PSS). The reactor cavity is also located in the bottom part of the sphere and it is constructed by concrete.

Several passive safety systems are located in the DRYWELL:

- External Heat Removal System (EHRS) – It consists of two big tanks with water (Refuel Water Storage Tanks - RWST), located outside the drywell. In each one of the RWSTs there are 2 heat exchangers (summary four), which collect and cool the steam from SGs. The steam condensates and returns to the bottom of SG helical pipes. This system has been used to cool the reactor primary side after reactor SCRAM followed by turbines stopping.
- Automatic Depressurization System (ADS-1) – A system of PRZ relief valves used to depressurized primary side in case of pressurizer level decreasing. The steam is removed in the Quench Tank (QT), where it is cooled and condensate.
- Automatic Depressurization System (ADS-2) – A system of PRZ relief valves, ADS-2 is connected directly to the drywell. It opens to equalize pressures between the RPV and DRYWELL when the difference between them is considerably low.
- The PSS is a passive system that serves to decrease the pressure in the containment. It consists of two tanks (common volume about 918 m³) located under the concrete plate, in the bottom hemisphere of the drywell. They are connected to the containment (upper hemisphere of the drywell) by two vent pipes. When the pressure in the containment is higher the steam enters into the vent pipes to the water volume of PSS, where it condensate. When the pressure in the containment became less than the PSS pressure a revers water flow from the PSS to the containment occurs through the vent pipes. This leads to reactor cavity filling with water and external reactor vessel water cooling (very promising mitigation strategy).
- The high pressure injection system consists of two Emergency Borated Tanks (EBT) installed in the containment above the concrete plate. The volume of each EBT is about 12.8 m³. The EBTs are able to makeup RPV on gravity through the connection with the DVI line. This connection opens when the PRZ pressure becomes less than about 117.2 bar.
- The low pressure injection system consists of two Long-term Gravity Makeup System tanks (LGMS). The total volume of the tanks is about 300 m³. They start to inject in DVI line when the difference between the RPV pressure and the containment pressure becomes less than about 0.5 bar.

Figure 1. Simplified scheme of generic SMR design

3. Description of the ASTECv3.1.1 computer code

To represent the behaviour of the SMR it has been used ICARE, CESAR, CPA, ISODOP, ELSA, SOPHAEROS modules of ASTECv3.1.1.

ICARE module of ASTEC is used to compute the thermo-chemical behaviour in the core. It includes many mechanical and thermo-chemical models that represent the processes in the core as well as core degradation and melt relocation into the LP, chemical interactions inside the core region and in the LP, heat exchanges by convection, conduction and radiation, release of FP till the vessel failure.

CESAR module defines the thermal-hydraulics in all primary and secondary side elements, as well as in the core channels. To describe the thermal-hydraulics and thermo-chemistry in the core ICARE and CESAR work together. The CPA module is used to represent the processes in the main zones of the containment (DRYWELL) as well as the zones QT, Quench Pipe (QP) and the ENVIRONMENT.

The ISODOP module is used for calculation of the decay heat after the reactor SCRAM. It also calculates the Fission Products (FP). The SOPHAEROS module calculates the FP release into the all volumes of primary side and into the zones of the containment (DW). The ELSA is a module that calculates FPs from the core.

4. Brief description of the Design2 input model

In the calculations it has been used DESIGN2_v6.1 ASTEC input model developed by ENEA (Italy) and modified by INRNE-BAS. This is an integral input model which represents all structural elements of the general design of this type of light water SMRs: core region, primary and secondary side and the passive safety systems, which ensure the safety work of SMR. Also the logics of the operation of all systems are implemented in the input.

All primary side is integrated in the vessel. In the primary side it was modelled the area of RPV above the core with riser channel in the middle of the vessel, PRZ at the top of the vessel, eight RCPs, eight SGs and eight downcomer channels. The scheme of RPV primary side is presented in Figure 2. The core region is positioned below the upper core plate. The core region is divided in 4 rings that separate four cylindrical channels, where the fuel assemblies and internal core components are placed. The core channels are surrounded by bypass and downcomer cylindrical channels. The bottom part of the vessel is so called LP. The LP vessel was divided in 4 rings radially and 23 segments axially, commonly in 92 meshes. RPV bottom part, where the core is located and the LP are modelled by 2D radial-axial geometry of the meshes for the ICARE code. The module CESAR models fluid channels meshes also with 2D geometry. The secondary side SG helical-coils are modelled inside the eight primary SGs channels.

The scheme of secondary side is presented in Figure 3. The external vessel pipes are connected with 4 heat exchangers in the RWSTs. All pipes are modelled as thermal-hydraulic volumes by CESAR. The passive safety systems are also modelled to work with CESAR model. The passive safety systems inside the drywell are presented in the scheme in Figure 4. It has been presented in the scheme the thermal-hydraulic volumes and the connections between them for PSS system, EBT (high pressure injection system) and LGMS (low pressure injection system).

For cavity modelling it was used External Reactor Vessel Cooling (ERVC) structure in ASTEC, which is a pipe to cool down the external face of a LP. The ERVC structure in a pipe structure that works with CESAR module of ASTEC. It contains 46 homogeneous volumes in height. Each one of these volumes is connected to the vessel wall segments modelled by ICARE (23 segments for LP

and 20 segments for the cylindrical part of the vessel to the elevation of the upper support plate). ERVC structure simulates external reactor vessel cooling. All other parts of the containment (Drywell) are modelled by CPA module of ASTEC. There are seven zones that represent the main parts of the DW including also the QT, QP and ENVIRONMENT. Some changes have been done by INRNE to improve the integral ASTEC model. An additional volume has been added between the ERVC volume (CESAR) and the bottom zone of Drywell (CPA) to optimize the liquid flow from the containment to the cavity.

Figure 2. Primary side

Figure 3. Secondary side

Figure 4. Passive safety systems in the DRYWELL

5. Results from the integral calculation with ASTECv3.1.1 computer code

The sequence of events is presented below:

Sequence of events:

1. 0.0 sec - Due to 2-inches double-ended guillotine break opening, on the DVI line, pressure in the containment start to rise.
2. 19.95 sec - SSIGNAL – “High containment pressure”, ($P_{drywel} > 1.7 \cdot 10^5$)

Due to SSIGNAL:

- 25.21 sec - Reactor SCRAM

- 25.21 sec - Turbine trip - Isolation of the secondary system
- 25.21 sec - Feedwater stop

The EHRS should start but it fails. The reactor cooling by the RWST is not possible. It creates conditions for SA with core overheating and degradation.

- 3. 90.21 sec - PCASTDOW signal – “Low pressurizer level”, (PRZ water level < 0.14 m)

Due to PCASTDOW:

- 105.33 sec - The 8th pumps coast down
- 105.33 sec - Check valves between RI and DC open ensuring the natural circulation
- 4. 307.11 sec - LMSIGNAL – “Low PRZ pressure”, (P_press < 117.2 bar)

Due to LMSIGNAL:

**The EBTs should start to deliver water in primary but they don’t start
The ADS-1 doesn’t open**

- 5. 3188 sec – Containment pressure increases to 13.5 bar that is the containment design pressure. Containment pressure dump below the PSS pressure and they blow to the containment filling the cavity with water.
- 6. 10400.3 sec - First cladding creep rupture. It started release of FP from the pellets.
- 7. 12586.8 sec – First material slump in the LP
- 8. 17664.8 sec – First slump with FP in the LP
- 9. 83423 sec – Large amount of corium (≈ 80 ton) slumps in the LP followed by two layers stratification
- 10. Around 127 000 sec – Second large amount of corium slumps (≈ 7 ton), two layers stratification
- 11. Around 300 000 sec – Beginning of cavity water depletion due to evaporation
- 12. 380265.0 sec - LDP_VCS signal – “Low DP between RPV and Containment”, ($dP < 5.04 \times 10^4$)

Due to signal LDP_VCS in the input model:

The LGMS tanks should start to deliver water in primary but they don’t open

- 13. Around 850 000 sec – Cavity water is completely evaporated
- 14. 914169 sec – Vessel failure (End of calculation).

Some of the final state of calculation (Figure 5) and the relative water levels in the cavity, containment and the break level (Figure 6) are presented in the figures below.

Figure 5. Final state at the end of calculation

Figure 6. Final state at the end of calculation

6. Simplified model for stand-alone calculation with ASTECv3.1.1 computer code

From the point of view of applying IVMR strategy with external vessel water cooling in the integral model this calculation is interesting from 83423 sec. (a big slump of corium in LP) till 300000 sec., because after that the water level in the cavity starts to decrease. Water evaporation from the cavity after that moment leads to vessel failure at 914169 sec. (10 days and 14 hours). The results from this calculation are used for preparing a simplified model for stand-alone calculation with ASTEC, which calculation will take considerably lower calculation time. The stand-alone input model is representing the processes in the vessel and cavity after the slump at 83423 sec. till 300000 sec. Initial and boundary conditions for the preparing of this stand-alone input model has been taken from the integral calculation.

In the stand-alone model the calculation starts at 83400 sec. and continues till 300 000 sec. Initial and boundary conditions for steady-state model calculation has been taken from the integral calculation. It has been modelled the vessel bottom elliptical part and the cylindrical part of vessel till the upper elevation 5.2373 (maximal core elevation). The elliptical part of the vessel (lower plenum) has been divided radially in 23 rings and axially in 16 segments.

The residual water inside the vessel at the beginning of calculation is 34230 kg. It corresponds to water level elevation in the vessel of 0.8 m at 83400 sec. It could be seen from Figure 7 that represents the collapsed water level in the core channel in the integral calculation.

The inside water temperature is 20 °C below the saturated water temperature accounted for the inside vessel pressure, which is 2 bar.

Outside of the vessel it has been modelled the reactor cavity by ERVC structure in ASTEC. This structure is used to define the cool down the external face of the LP and cylindrical VESSEL part to the maximal core elevation. Each mesh of the external face of the VESSEL and LP is associated to a volume from ERVC pipe. The pipe volumes and the LP external meshes begin from the lowest elevation. The temperature of the water in ERVC is 373 K (273 °C) but the outside pressure in ERVC is 1.6 bar.

Figure 7. Core channel collapsed water level in integral calculation

Figure 8. Magma slumps from the core to the LP in integral calculation

At 83423 sec. it started slumping of magma into the LP. It consists of melted reactor fuel and melted in-vessel structures. Two big slumps are indicated during the integral calculation (see Figure 8). The first one starts at 83423 sec. Approximately 80 ton are poured from the core region

into the LP in 300 sec. The second one starts at 127000 sec. and has mass of approximately 7 tons. It continues nearly 3000 sec.

The slumps mass and composition correspond to these in the integral calculation. The masses and compositions of the slumps are presented in the Table 1 and Table 2 below:

Table 1. Composition of the first slump of 80 ton at 83423 sec into the LP

Component	Mass	Temperature
UO ₂	42 ton	2820 K
ZrO ₂	7.4 ton	2820 K
ZrO	4.0 ton	2820 K
Zr	0.3 ton	2820 K
SSTEEL	26.3 ton	2820 K

Table 2. Composition of the second slump of 7 ton at 127000 sec into the LP

Component	Mass	Temperature
UO ₂	2 ton	2800 K
ZrO ₂	0.5 ton	2800 K
ZrO	0.5 ton	2800 K
Zr	0.0 ton	2800 K
SSTEEL	4 ton	2800 K

The residual power from 83423 sec. to 300000 sec. for 55000 kg UO₂ has, accounted from the integral calculation is presented below (Table 3). It is used in the stand-alone calculation the column which pointed residual power per 1 kg UO₂.

Table 3. Decay heat

Time	Residual power	Residual power per 1 kg UO ₂ (55t)	Time	Residual power	Residual power per 1 kg UO ₂ (55t)
8.34285E+004 sec	4.55360E+006 W	82.47 W/kg	2.00031E+005 sec	3.56174E+006 W	64.75 W/kg
1.00028E+005 sec	4.35064E+006 W	79.10 W/kg	2.20031E+005 sec	3.45213E+006 W	62.77 W/kg
1.20029E+005 sec	4.14274E+006 W	75.32 W/kg	2.40031E+005 sec	3.35217E+006 W	60.95 W/kg
1.40031E+005 sec	3.96746E+006 W	72.13 W/kg	2.60031E+005 sec	3.26059E+006 W	59.28 W/kg
1.60031E+005 sec	3.81690E+006 W	69.39 W/kg	2.80031E+005 sec	3.17636E+006 W	57.75 W/kg
1.80131E+005 sec	3.68201E+006 W	66.94 W/kg	2.99981E+005 sec	3.09881E+006 W	56.34 W/kg

For this stand-alone calculation just CESAR and ICARE modules of ASTECv3.1.1 have been used. They work in a coupled mode to represent in-vessel events phenomenology. CESAR models the thermal-hydraulics in the LP channel. The channel is modelled with water and with structural internals. The level of the water is the same as in the integral calculation at the moment of the first slump of corium in the LP. ICARE module computes the thermochemical phase separation and stratification of the pool and the melting of the vessel lower head.

7. Comparison of the results from the integral calculation and the results from stand-alone model calculation

The comparison between the integral and stand-alone calculation surf for validation of the stand-alone model and increases the confidence in the ASTEC computer code and in the stand-alone input model. In this case the validated stand-alone model could be used further for uncertainty

and sensitivity investigations, which is almost impossible with the integral input model due to the extremely longest computational time. The comparison between the results from the stand-alone calculation and the integral calculation till 300000 sec. is presented below.

Integral calculation

Figure 9. Corium slumps composition (Integral calculation)

Stand-alone calculation

Figure 10. Corium slumps composition (Stand-alone calculation)

At Figure 9 and Figure 10 it is presented corium injection composition. As the initial and boundary conditions in the stand-alone calculation have been taken from the integral one it could be seen that the compositions of the slumps in the both are the same. The amounts of UO_2 , ZrO_2 , Zr and SSTEEL correspond also with the values pointed in the Table 1 and Table 2.

Figure 11. Oxide layer composition (Integral calculation)

Figure 12. Oxide layer composition (Stand-alone calculation)

After the first huge slump at 83423 sec. the corium stratifies in two layers: oxide layer at the bottom and metal layer at the top. The density of the oxide layer is 8200 kg/m^3 but the density of the light metal layer is 7500 kg/m^3 . At Figure 11 and Figure 12 are presented the behaviours and the compositions at the oxide layer in the both calculations. The both calculations show very closed results.

At Figure 13 and Figure 14 are presented the light metal compositions. As it seen from the figures the both calculations indicate similar behaviour. Nevertheless, there are some small differences. As it shown in Figure 13 and Figure 14 the light metal layer in the integral calculation

indicates a little bit higher amount of stainless steel (the Fe is around 29 tons after the equilibrium quasi-state) in comparison with the steady-state calculation (the Fe is around 27 tons after the equilibrium quasi-state). It is due to differences in the vessel ablation. The vessel LP ablation begins immediately after the corium slump and stratification, when the decay heat in the melt is higher. Vessel ablation continues for short period of time. The ablated stainless steel from the vessel wall is incorporated to the stratified corium pool preliminary to the light metal layer. When the decay heat decreases in time the external vessel water cooling absorbs the generated in the corium heat and it leads the system to a stable equilibrium condition. It looks like the ablation in the integral calculation is a little more intensive than in the stand-alone calculation.

Figure 13. Light metal layer composition (Integral calculation)

Figure 14. Light metal layer composition (Stand-alone calculation)

Figure 15. Temperature field (Integral calculation)

Figure 16. Temperature field (Stand-alone calculation)

The final state of the calculations at 300000 sec. could be seen at Figure 15 and Figure 16. The pictures show also the different nodalization of the LP. In the integral calculation the LP is divided in 23 axial segments and 4 radial rings. In the stand-alone calculation the LP nodalization includes 16 axial segments and 23 radial rings. It could be seen the two layered stratification of the corium and the vessel ablation at the elevation of the light metal layer. Also the picture of temperature field shows the temperatures of the different structural elements.

Figure 17. Final thickness of the LP vessel at 300000 sec (Integral calculation)

Figure 18. Final thickness of the LP vessel at 300000 sec (Stand-alone calculation)

The final shapes of the LP vessel in the integral and in the stand-alone calculation could be seen in Figure 17 and Figure 18. The vessel thickness evaluates from the bottom of LP - 19 cm to the top of LP - 28 cm. In the integral calculation the minimal thickness of the vessel (0.192 m) due to ablation is observed at segment 15 between elevations -1.07 and -1.12 at the place of contact with the light metal layer. In the stand-alone calculation the minimal thickness (0.192 m) is observed at segment 11 between the elevations -0.99 m and -1.06 m.

The integral calculation indicates a little bit higher section of ablation (the significantly ablated segments are four). In the stand-alone calculation there are two segments with higher ablation. The ablated stainless steel from the vessel wall is included in the corium melt pool and preliminary to the light metal layer due to it has lower density. It could be seen in comparison between Figure 17 and Figure 18. The masses of stainless steel components in the integral calculation are a little bit higher than in the stand-alone calculation.

8. Conclusions

The results from the integral calculation and the stand-alone calculation indicates very good convergence. The both input models have ERVC pipe structure, which simulates the external LP vessel water cooling (applying the IVMR strategy with external vessel water cooling) due to cavity filling with water. Although the different nasalization of the reactor bottom part (LP) the phenomena that occurs after corium slumps show similar behaviour and the vessel ablation occurs at the almost one and the same elevations in the calculations. The minimal vessel thickness is the same in the both calculations (19.2 cm). In the stand-alone input model there were not modelled the changes in the outside pressure and the changes in the outside water temperature. It has been used a user decision the outside pressure to has constant value (1.6 bar), equal to the outside pressure value accounted from the integral calculation at the time of the first significant slump. This is applied for the outside water temperature. The cavity water temperature is with 20 °C degree less than the saturated temperature for 1.6 bar. Actually, the cavity water temperature has a constant value. This difference between the integral and the stand-alone calculation leads to reaching higher heat fluxes in the integral calculation. Variations in the outside pressure lead

to violating the subcooling margin close to the vessel wall. Outside pressure drops cause water boiling. It disturbs the heat transfer and increases the HF in the integral calculation.

Based on the presented analysis it could be stated, that the using of constant parameters for external pressure and temperature gives very closed results to the integral calculation.

Nevertheless, the stand-alone input is validated against the integral calculation with sufficient degree of confidence. In this way the stand-alone input model for ASTEC could be used for further uncertainty and sensitivity investigations of the main phenomena during the IVMR strategy applying with external vessel water cooling.

This investigation shows that the ASTEC computer code could be applied with a good confidence for simulation of the main phenomena that occurs in the generic light water iPWR during the late phase of the accident with applying the IVMR strategy with external vessel water cooling. The both input models: the integral one and the stand-alone input model indicate similar behaviour and could be used for further investigations.

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